

Notes

Synthesis and Characterisation of Copper(II) Complexes of 4-Amino-3-hydrazino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole

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Manuscript received 7 November 1991, revised 19 May 1992, accepted 18 June 1992

Substituted triazoles are biologically active compounds and they are reported to act as bactericides, pesticides and potential fungicides¹, and as such, it becomes interesting to study their metal chelates. Solid and very stable 4-amino-3-hydrazino-5-mercapto-1,2,4-triazole has been selected and used as ligand. Its complexing behaviour and different physicochemical properties of the new complexes formed, have been investigated. The results are based on various analytical and spectral data.

Results and Discussion

All the complexes (Table 1) are insoluble in common organic solvent, such as methanol, ethanol, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride and benzene, and fairly soluble in DMF. Their conductivities were measured in DMF and found to be 7.39 for $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{AHMTH}$, 135.6 for $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{AHMTH}$, 245.32 for $\text{Cu}(\text{ac})_2 \cdot 2\text{AHMTH}$ and 79.32 for $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{AHMTH}$, which indicate the non-electrolytic nature of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{AHMTH}$ and presence of 3, 3 and 2 ions in other complexes respectively. Except $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{AHMTH}$ all other complexes gave positive tests for the presence of the coordination sphere. The absence of ionic chloride indicates the presence of the chloride ion in the coordination sphere. Magnetic moments of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{AHMTH}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 3\text{AHMTH}$, $\text{Cu}(\text{ac})_2 \cdot 2\text{AHMTH}$ and $\text{CuSO}_4 \cdot 3\text{AHMTH}$ were found to be 0.98, 0.99, 1.19 and 0.919 B.M. respectively, which indicate the presence of one unpaired electron in each of them. This sub-normal value of magnetic moment may be due to polymeric nature of the complexes and some degree of metal-metal interaction².

On the basis of the values obtained it may be suggested that these complexes have dimeric structures in which magnetic exchange takes place probably by means of overlap of $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbitals.

Ir spectra: There is a medium broad band at $3\ 500\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ in the ir spectrum of $[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{ac})_2$ and no such band is present either in the spectra of the ligand or other Cu^{II} complexes, indicating the presence of coordinated water molecules. This observation is further supported by strong shoulder at 1 600, weak broad band at 860 and a weak band at $370\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ which are attributed to $\delta_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$, $\pi_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}$ and ν_{CuO} modes of vibrations³. There are four medium bands at 3 220, 3 190, 3 070 and $3\ 610\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ in the spectrum of the ligand due to the interaction between ν_{NH} and ν_{NH_2} mode of vibrations⁴. It indicates thione form of the ligand. However, weak broad band at $2\ 350\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ can be assigned to ν_{SH} mode of vibration⁵ indicating thiol form of ligand.

In $[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_2 \cdot (\text{NO}_3)_2]$, the ν_{SH} band is observed almost at the same position indicating the presence of thiol form of the ligand and absence of bonding through sulphur. In $[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{ac})_2$ and $[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_3]\text{SO}_4$, the ν_{SH} band splits and is observed at 2 340, 2 330, and 2 330, $2\ 300\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ respectively. This may be due to hydrogen bonding of the SH hydrogen with acetate and sulphate anions in the crystal lattice of these complexes.

Very strong band at $1\ 630\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ in the spectrum of the ligand is due to δ_{NH} mode of vibration. This band splits in $[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ and red-shifts about $10\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ in the other Cu^{II} complexes which indicates coordination of the ligand through amino nitrogen atom. The ligand contains a thiomide group.

An analysis of the thiomide bands gives the following information⁶. (i) Strong band at $1\ 590$ and $1\ 500\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ (thiomide band I) in the ligand and the red-shifting of the first band ($1\ 590\ \text{cm}^{-1}$) by about $70\ \text{cm}^{-1}$ in all the Cu^{II} complexes indicate coordination through amino nitrogen⁷. (ii) Medium strong bands (thiomide band II) at 1 460 and $1\ 330$

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF COMPLEXES

Compd.	Analysis % : Found					
	C	H	N	N	S	Cl
Ligand (AHMTH)	16.21	4.11	58.01	—	22.00	—
$[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_2 \cdot (\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{ac})_2$	18.62	4.23	38.51	12.40	12.58	—
$[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_3]\text{SO}_4$	12.3	3.13	43.62	10.58	16.52	—
$[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_2\text{Cl}_2]$	11.45	2.80	38.97	14.32	15.2	16.45
$[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_3 \cdot (\text{NO}_3)_2]$	11.32	2.86	44.52	10.2	15.25	—

cm^{-1} get split and are observed at 1 430, 1 350 and 1 280 cm^{-1} in $[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_2\text{Cl}_2]$, at 1 420, 1 390 and 1 350 cm^{-1} in $[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_3]\text{SO}_4$ and red-shifted at 1 430 cm^{-1} in $[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_3](\text{NO}_3)_2$ and at 1 390 cm^{-1} in $[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_2(\text{N}_2\text{O})_2](\text{ac})_2$, which suggest bonding through sulphur⁸. (iii) Strong bands at 1 090 and 1 040 cm^{-1} (thiimide band III) are slightly red-shifted (10 cm^{-1}) in all the Cu^{II} complexes which indicate coordination through thione sulphur. (iv) There is a very strong band at 1 100–1 050 cm^{-1} and weak band at 740 cm^{-1} in $[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_3]\text{SO}_4$ which indicate the presence of ionic sulphate⁵. (v) There is a very broad band at 1 360 cm^{-1} in $[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_3](\text{NO}_3)_2$, which indicates the presence of the nitrate group in the ionic form⁵.

Electronic spectra: There is a strong band at 280 and 360 nm in the spectrum of the ligand assigned due to $n \rightarrow \pi^*$ and $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transitions respectively. These bands get shifted to 267 and 332 nm in $[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_3](\text{NO}_3)_2$, 268, 330 nm in $[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ and 268, 330 nm in $[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_2(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{ac})_2$ complexes respectively, indicating coordination of the ligand through sulphur⁹.

The magnetic moment values of all the Cu^{II} complexes indicate d^9 configurations for them having 3D free-ion term. The 2D free-ion term splits in a regular octahedral environment into lower 2E_g and upper $^2T_{2g}$ levels¹⁰.

In the present investigation, the Cu^{II} complexes display band at 403 nm due to charge transfer and inter-ligand electronic transition. The weak band at 566 nm in $[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_2\text{Cl}_2]$, at 570 nm in $[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_3](\text{NO}_3)_2$, at 600 nm $[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_3]\text{SO}_4$ and at 578 nm in $[\text{Cu}(\text{AHMTH})_3(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2](\text{ac})_2$ complexes are assigned reasonably to $^2E_g \rightarrow ^2T_{2g}$ transition, and distorted octahedral geometry may be suggested for all the Cu^{II} complexes.

Experimental

The ligand (AHMTH) was synthesised by heating thiourea (78 g, extra pure) and hydrazine hydrate (115 ml) for 2.5 h with stirring on a water-bath. The reaction mixture was allowed to stand for about 30 min and then poured in 2 N

HCl (500 ml). The sulphur was removed by filtration. The filtrate was neutralised by 2 N NaOH and the resulting white solid was crystallised from boiling water (1000 : 1) as colourless crystals, m.p. 268°.

The metal complexes: The Cu^{II} complexes were prepared by adding dropwise an aqueous solution of the metal salt to a slightly alkaline solution (NaOH) of the ligand, and the resulting solution was placed on a hot plate ($\sim 100^\circ$) for 1 h. It was then cooled and the resulting solid was washed with water and dried (110°).

All the chemicals used were of B.D.H. or equivalent grade.

Infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 021 spectrophotometer and the electronic spectra (nujol) on a Bechmann DU-6 spectrophotometer. Magnetic susceptibility measurement was carried out on a Gouy balance.

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Prof. B. P. Verma, Head, Department of Chemistry, Magadh University, Bodh-Gaya for facilities and discussions and to authorities of C.D.R.I., Lucknow, for recording ir spectra.

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